

The Draft Genome of *Globodera ellingtonae*

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Abstract: *Globodera ellingtonae* is a newly described potato cyst nematode (PCN) found in Idaho, Oregon, and Argentina. Here, we present a genome assembly for *G. ellingtonae*, a relative of the quarantine nematodes *G. pallida* and *G. rostochiensis*, produced using data from Illumina and Pacific Biosciences DNA sequencing technologies.

Key words: genome, *Globodera ellingtonae*, potato cyst nematode.

PCN are a global problem estimated to cause losses of 9% of total potato production worldwide (Turner and Rowe, 2006). The recent genome projects for *Globodera pallida* and *G. rostochiensis* contribute to the understanding and control of these economically important plant-parasitic nematodes (Cotton et al., 2014; Eves-van den Akker et al., 2016). A recently described PCN, *Globodera ellingtonae* (Handoo et al., 2012), is a close relative of *G. rostochiensis* and *G. pallida*. Here, we report on the genome sequencing and assembly of an Oregon strain of *G. ellingtonae*, likely the result of a substantial population bottleneck, providing a new avenue for understanding the evolution and biology of PCN.

We assembled the genome of *G. ellingtonae* using HiSeq and MiSeq reads and the de novo assembler Allpaths-LG (Gnerre et al., 2011), followed by gap filling with PBJelly using PacBio reads (English et al., 2012). Sequencing libraries were constructed from *G. ellingtonae* DNA extracted using a Qiagen DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Valencia, CA) from second-stage juveniles hatched from several hundred cysts ($n = 200$) collected at Powell Butte, Oregon. MiSeq sequencing was performed for 301×2 cycles (paired-end); HiSeq sequencing was performed for 100×2 cycles (paired-end) for two mate pair libraries (~3 and ~8 kb inserts); and PacBio sequencing was performed on eight SMRTcells with 3 to 20 kb libraries. The MiSeq and PacBio DNA sequencing used the same original DNA extraction; the HiSeq run used a separate extraction performed later with ~500 cysts. Quality filtering and trimming of the Illumina reads were performed using the program Trimmomatic (Bolger et al., 2014); PacBio reads were corrected with MiSeq reads using the program WGS module pacBioToCA (Koren et al., 2012). To fulfill the Allpaths-LG assembly program requirement of short insert paired-end reads, single unpaired MiSeq reads were split into two overlapping

165 bp fastq sequences to mimic paired-end reads from a library with ~270 bp inserts. Percent reads used in the assembly were 69.9%, 50.6%, and 36.3% for the MiSeq, 3 kb HiSeq, and 8 kb HiSeq libraries, respectively, with final sequence coverages of 67.6, 50.5, and 27.0 for each. We screened for contamination using a blastn search of the GenBank microbe “Representative genomes” database, resulting in the removal of eight scaffolds, all <2 kb.

The final assembly contained 2,248 scaffolds, a number smaller than those resulting for the published assemblies of *G. rostochiensis* (4,377 scaffolds) and *G. pallida* (6,873 scaffolds). The final *G. ellingtonae* assembly totaled 119,060,168 bp, similar to the *G. rostochiensis* and *G. pallida* assemblies (95.9 and 124.6 Mb, respectively). The longest *G. ellingtonae* scaffold was 2.8 Mb (compared to 0.7 Mb for *G. rostochiensis* and 0.6 Mb for *G. pallida*), and 15 scaffolds were >1 Mbp. The final *G. ellingtonae* assembly had a scaffold N50 of 360 kb (89 kb for *G. rostochiensis* and 122 kb for *G. pallida*), contained 11.7% gaps (5% for *G. rostochiensis* and 17% for *G. pallida*), and had a GC content of 37% (38% for *G. rostochiensis* and 37% for *G. pallida*).

To assess completeness of the *G. ellingtonae* assembly, the program CEGMA (Parra et al., 2007) was used to search for 248 core eukaryotic genes (CEG). At least partial transcripts were detected for 239 (96%) of the CEGs, with complete transcripts for 229 (92%). These values were similar to those for the *G. rostochiensis* genome (96% partial and 94% complete), and higher than those for *G. pallida* (81% partial and 74% complete). We further compared the *G. ellingtonae* genome to that of *G. rostochiensis* by using the 14,309 predicted proteins from the latter species as queries in blast searches against the former species’ genome. Using an identity cutoff of 60%, we found hits for 14,104 (98.6%) of the proteins; 13,946 (97.4%) hits were found using a more conservative cutoff of 80%. The *G. ellingtonae* genome provides a valuable resource for study of the evolution in the PCN lineage.

GenBank accession numbers: The raw DNA sequence data and genome assembly were deposited at GenBank under BioSample no. SAMN04393202.

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